

Daytime and Nighttime NO₂ retrievals with the MkIV Brewer spectrophotometer

Software description and manual

1. Introduction

Brewer spectrophotometers can retrieve the column concentration of certain trace gases in the atmosphere by analysing the direct irradiance from the sun or the moon, or the radiance from the zenith sky, collected at different wavelengths.

Ozone retrievals during both day and night from the Brewer spectrophotometer can be performed with software available to the Brewer users community, such as the Brewer Processing Software (BPS) provided by Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) or Martin Stanek's O3Brewer [<http://www.o3soft.eu/>].

In contrast, nitrogen dioxide retrievals from MkIV Brewer spectrophotometers are still a research task, particularly during nighttime. These retrievals have not been implemented on a large scale due to the need for specific instrument characterisation and the unavailability of a travelling standard for calibration. This document provides an overview of the algorithm steps and the codes used for nitrogen dioxide retrievals. The software is intended for advanced users only. The interested reader can learn the basics of the Brewer retrievals from the bibliographic references at the end of this document.

Developers using the code or its parts must acknowledge the author and the QA4EO project.

2. Step-by-step guide to the nitrogen dioxide retrievals

Below is a step-by-step guide for nitrogen dioxide retrievals. The Brewer must be first characterised as accurately as possible to calculate the parameters in the retrieval equation and account for the interfering factors. Indeed, since NO₂ is a weak absorber of solar radiation, its retrievals are susceptible to interferences related to instrumental effects or atmospheric species other than the ones being investigated. The following characteristics must be determined:

1. **Dispersion function** of the grating/monochromator: This function relates the microsteps of the motor rotating the diffraction grating to the wavelengths corresponding to the monochromator exit slits. The dispersion function is determined using data collected from the dispersion test ("dsp") during the instrument calibration performed by a specialised company and based on a lamp with a known emission line spectrum. Normally, the test is conducted only in the UV region of the spectrum, but it is advisable to request it for the visible region as well as for NO₂ retrievals. Alternatively, an approximation of the dispersion function in the visible region can be derived by multiplying the UV dispersion by 2/3 (using the diffraction grating formula, considering that Brewer measurements in the visible are obtained in the second diffraction order and UV in the third). The analytical function of the dispersion relation is obtained using the physical model described by Gröbner et al., 1998.

2. **Passband (resolution)** of the spectrophotometer: The full width at half maximum (FWHM) at the operational microstep of the diffraction grating is obtained from the same data of the previous test through a linear fit between microsteps and FWHM for each combination of emission line/slit.
3. **Sensitivity to spectral misalignment errors**: This is calculated by using a high-resolution extraterrestrial irradiance spectrum, applying the Bouguer-Lambert-Beer equation for each wavelength, considering Rayleigh scattering and absorption by major trace gases, and calculating the derivative of the resulting spectrum with respect to wavelength using the finite difference method.
4. **Weighting coefficients** of the linear combination: These coefficients are used in the retrieval algorithm (differential absorption) to combine the solar irradiance collected at the measured wavelengths, removing the interference from atmospheric absorbers within the same wavelength range as nitrogen dioxide, as well as certain instrumental factors, and maximizing NO₂ sensitivity.
5. **Differential cross section** of nitrogen dioxide: This is obtained by convolving the spectral cross section of NO₂ (e.g., spectroscopic data from Vandaele et al., 1998, at a temperature of 254.5 K) with the slit function of each slit (parameterised with a trapezoidal function) and subsequently weighting it with the coefficients calculated in the previous step.
6. **Calculation of the differential Rayleigh scattering coefficient**: This is based on the operational wavelengths (dispersion relation), weightings, and the scattering cross section from Bodhaine et al., 1999.
7. **Interferences** from unaccounted atmospheric absorbers: For example, oxygen dimer (O₂-O₂) and water vapour. Their determination involves linearly combining the corresponding cross section (after convolution with the Brewer slit function) with the weightings.
8. **Spectral attenuation of Brewer neutral density filters** for each wavelength and filter used. Since these filters introduce slight variations in the colour of the radiation entering the monochromator, they must be characterised accurately by measuring the attenuation of the radiation emitted by the Brewer's internal halogen lamp (standard lamp). Additionally, since some filters are optically very thick, many measurements (e.g., two months, every night when the Brewer is not measuring) will be needed to minimise statistical noise. The obtained attenuation must also be weighted according to the previous steps.
9. **Sensitivity to the internal instrument temperature**. This is determined by applying the algorithm to the irradiance from the internal lamp and performing a linear regression against the instrument temperature.

The necessary source codes have been provided along with this guide and are described below.

2.1 Step 1

Objective: Determine the dispersion function and resolution based on the instrumental characterisation. The physical model is based on Göbner et al., 1998

Input data: W files from dispersion test

Script(s): `dispersion.m` and `complete_o3.m`

Usage: Modify the Matlab/Octave script `dispersion.m` in the following way:

- `WDIR`: Set the working directory

- ``DEAD_TIME``, ``OP_STEP``, ``ZERO``: Set these values according to your Brewer's configuration
- ``lineSlit``: Set the matrix according to the reliable line/slit combinations from the dispersion test
- ``W...067``: Adjust the wildcard characters according to the files to be processed

Run ``dispersion.m``. This will create several files. Then run ``complete_o3.m`` using ``disp_coeff.txt`` generated from the previous step as the argument.

2.2 Step 2

Objective: Calculate the weightings of the linear combination and the NO₂ differential absorption coefficient using the wavelengths and FWHM from the dispersion test, as well as the spectroscopic data from Vandaele et al., 1998, at a temperature of 254.5 K

Input data: Files from Step 1 (``disp_coeff.txt``, ``resolution.txt``), cross section files, solar spectrum

Additional requirements: libRadtran radiative transfer model [<http://libradtran.org>], not provided

Script(s): ``misal.m``

Usage: Modify the Matlab/Octave script ``misal.m`` according to the site characteristics and your PC configuration:

- ``uvspec.pressure``: Average pressure of the site (also update SCDRAY accordingly)
- ``uvspec.o3``: Average ozone column
- ``uvspec.alpha`` and ``uvspec.beta``: Average aerosol Angstrom parameters
- ``uvspec.datapath``: Path of the libRadtran data files
- ``LATITUDE``, ``LONGITUDE``, ``ALTITUDE``: Geographical coordinates of the site
- ``STEPNO2``: Operating step of your Brewer

The script will calculate the weightings (``gNO2``) and the differential cross section (``diffCoeffNO2``) to remove the effect of the scattering/absorption by other atmospheric gases and the effect of slight wavelength shifts. The results are provided for a total of 4, 5 and 6 wavelengths, depending on the number of wavelengths used for the retrievals (normally 6 for daytime retrievals and 5 for nighttime retrievals).

2.3 Step 3

Objective: Assess the effect of interferences by known atmospheric absorbers (O₃, O₂-O₂) on NO₂ retrievals

Input data: Dispersion coefficients and resolution from Step 1, weightings from Step 2

Script(s): ``o3_calc.m``, ``o4_hermans.m`` and ``o4_calc.m``

Usage: Modify the Matlab/Octave scripts ``o3_calc.m`` and ``o4_calc.m`` as in Step 2. Change atmospheric parameters in ``o4_hermans.m`` according to the considered station.

The ``o3_calc.m`` script provides the ratio (``xs_ratio``) between the ozone differential absorption coefficient and the NO₂ differential absorption coefficient. The error due to unaccounted ozone on NO₂ retrievals will be:

$$O_3 \text{ slant column} * xs_ratio / \text{airmass}$$

`xs_ratio` is an input of the NO₂ retrieval software (Step 7).

As for the oxygen dimer, the `o4_calc.m` script provides the error due to O₂-O₂ on NO₂ retrievals (`O4eff`). This is also an input to the retrieval software (Step 7). The oxygen dimer cross sections are calculated using the `o4_hermans.m` script. For Rome, they were precalculated and stored in the `o4_Rome.txt` file (provided).

2.4 Step 4

Objective: Assess the effects of ND filter transmittance

Input data: Weighting coefficients from Step 1

Additional requirements: The routine `JF` should have been run for several weeks before the analysis to collect as much data as possible about the spectral transmittance of the filters.

Script(s): `jf_an.m`, `all_jf.pl`, `average.m`, `filter_corr_alternative.m`

Usage: Ensure that `filter_corr_alternative.m` points to the correct files. Before running `filter_corr_alternative.m`, execute `all_jf.pl` in the directory where the `JF` files were copied.

2.5 Step 5

Objective: Conversion of Brewer B-files into a tabular format that can be digested by the next scripts

Input data: Brewer B-files

Script(s): `bform.pl`

Usage: Set the Brewer number in `bform.pl` and run the script. It will produce a set of files in tabular format.

2.6 Step 6

Objective: Calculate the extraterrestrial coefficient (ETC) needed for NO₂ retrievals

Input data: Output from all previous steps

Additional requirements: A pre-run (with any ETC) of the retrieval is needed (Step 7) to produce the `fn.dat` file with corrected counts

Script(s): `mle_and_bm_high_freq.R`

Usage: Check `config.R` file. Also check the additional configuration parameters in the script `mle_and_bm_high_freq.R`. The script will calculate an estimate of the ETC based on statistical methods, notably the bootstrap estimation (BE) and the Minimum-amount Langley Extrapolation (MLE). Usually, a step of 6 month is appropriate to capture the sensitivity changes in the Brewer while keeping the estimates accurate. Refer to Diémoz et al., 2021 and Herman et al., 2009 for further details.

2.7 Step 7

Objective: Perform the NO₂ retrievals

Input data: Output from all previous steps

Additional requirements: SPICE Toolkit from NASA to calculate the Moon ephemerides, not provided [<https://naif.jpl.nasa.gov/naif/toolkit.html>]

Script(s): ``bproc_fm2.R`` (moon) and ``bproc.R`` (sun)

Usage: Edit the configuration file (``config.R``) to include the correct paths for all files needed by the script. Copy and paste the values obtained from the previous steps, then run the R script.

2.8 Step 8

Objective: Assess the effect of internal temperature on NO₂ retrievals

Input data: Output from all previous steps

Script(s): ``bproc_sl.R``

Usage: The script estimates the effect of the instrumental temperature by simulating the NO₂ retrieval based on the spectral irradiance from the internal lamp instead of the sun. By plotting the linear combination as a function of the internal temperature, it is possible to find the (usually linear) function representing the Brewer sensitivity to internal temperature. Include this function in the ``config.R`` file as ``temperature.correction.ratio``. Repeat Step 7 using the updated config file.

2.9 Step 9

Objective: Perform cloud screening and calculate the combined uncertainty

Input data: Output from all previous steps

Script(s): ``cloud_screening_Uncertainty_and_final_dataset.R``

Usage: Edit the script to customise the analysis and the output. Run the R script after performing NO₂ retrievals (Step 7). The output is stored in the ``N02_Brewer067_BNALG2.csv`` file.

Note: The current script only works for direct-sun measurements. An update for moon measurements will be released after further investigation of possible systematic effects. Refer to Diémoz et al., 2021 for further details.

2.10 Step 10

Objective: Convert to GEOMS data format

Input data: ``fn.dat`` (moon) or ``ds.dat`` (sun) from Step 7

Script(s): ``write_GEOMS.R``

Usage: Edit the script to customise the output, e.g. details of Principal Investigator, etc. In particular, choose ``geometry`` (“lunar” or “solar”) and check that the ``input_file`` variable points to the correct output file from Step 7. The script will create NetCDF output files based on the harmonised GEOMS data format.

Bibliographic references

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